

**MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF
TRAUMATOLOGICAL, ORTHOPEDICS AND NEUROSURGICAL
DISEASES**

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ABSTRACT. This study attempted to investigate that what are modern approaches in this era for the treatment of some diseases related to condition such as traumatological, orthopaedic Condition which related to neurological disease. Every positive situation is negative impact also there are also a number of difficulties where emerged while performing this surgeries.

KEY WORDS: technology, traumatological, orthopaedic, therapy, medical.

INTRODUCTION

Medical devices are considered to be the crucial for the services offered in prevention,, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of illness and diseases. Everyday more than 50,000 different kind of medical devices are estimated to be used in healthcare facilities and in all over the world.

Since the declaration of alma ATA in 1978, WHO has highlighted the importance of appropriate technologies and has called for better standardisation of health and medical technologies.

Main body. In this modern era, a lot of technology has advanced, like Medical Sciences has improved a lot in this. Since January 2023 at the department of orthopaedics and Acibadem Sistine hospital, A new method for treatment of orthopedics diseases with application of home stem cell(mesenchymal stem cells) begin to applied which considered to be the significant step forward in the field of orthopedics And the development of orthobiology.

If we talk about rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis mesenchymal stem cells delay cartilage degeneration progression and lead to pain relief and improved functions in patients. The procedure involves using a patient own stem cells, which have the unique property of being able to develop into many different cell types and functions to treat sports injuries and arthritis.

Neurosurgical conditions is the surgery of nervous system it is a medical speciality concerned with diagnosis and treatment of patient with injury or

disease of the brain, spinal cord and spinal column. In the top clinics of Israel, an average of 3000 neurosurgical operations are performed per year. To accurately diagnose a tumour, doctor uses fluorescent diagnostic (for example ALA-5), which clearly defines the boundary of the tumour often they uses PETSCANNING is one of the most informative method of malignant neoplasm diagnostic. Some types of Timor are treated without direct surgery. Thanks to the innovative CYBER KNIFE and GAMMA KNIFE devices.

Microsurgical and minimal invasive techniques allows the patient to recovers quickly after surgery. Patient spends only 1-2 days and can be discharge only in a week after the operation on the brain.

Traumatology is the primary response for the professionals all over the world who study and treat people exposed to highly stressful and traumatic events.

PTSD- POST TRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER is an anxiety disorder caused by very stressful, frightening or distressing events. CBT- COGNITIVE BEHAVIOURAL THERAPY is the modern treatment focuses on the relationships among the thoughts , feeling and behaviours , targets the current problems and symptoms and focuses on changing pattern of behaviour, thoughts and feelings that leads to difficulties in functioning. Also there is a therapy called trauma-focused therapy is a specific approach to therapy that is built on the understating of how traumatic expression affect an individual's mental, emotions and help children, adolescents and adult survivors heals from the effect of trauma.

CONCLUSION

This research has enlightening a wide range of techniques and procedure during that are used while performing some medical conditions such as traumatic, orthopedics or conditions which are related with neurosurgical disease.it involves the treatment like we treated conditions like osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis treated with their own mesenchymal stem cells.in conditions such as neurosurgical disorder like surgery of nervous system, disease related with brain, spinal cord and spinal column.

Brain related tumour is removes with techniques like PET SCANNING or by using devices such as CYBER KNIFE and GAMMA KNIFE. It also uses microsurgical and minimal invasive techniques which patient used to recover quickly. And in the cases of traumatologically conditions like PTSD (POST TRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER) which is an anxiety or stress disorder which can be cured by given CBT (COGNITIVE BEHAVIOURAL THERAPY).

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